

Separating Si phases from diagenetically-modified sediments through sequential leaching

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ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Oleg Pokrovsky

ABSTRACT

Silicon (Si) phases such as biogenic silica, lithogenic silicate and authigenic silica/silicate in marine sediments provide valuable information about past Si cycling. Wet-chemical sequential leaching methods are often applied to extract different Si phases from marine sediments to study Si diagenetic processes in shallow subsurface. The potential of this method to separate Si phases from deeply-buried and diagenetically-modified sediments has not been systematically examined. We applied a sequential leaching protocol to drill core sediments retrieved from the Ulleung Basin, East/Japan Sea. We performed geochemical (elemental abundance and stable Si isotopes, $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) and microscopic (X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscope) analyses to monitor leaching efficiency in separating different Si phases. We show that, prior to alkaline leaching, applying weak acid is able to remove metal oxide and/or clay-like phases. The following Na_2CO_3 leaching, based on a commonly-adopted protocol, is able to dissolve some but not all diatoms. The results of elemental contents and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values of leachates suggest that, in diagenetically-modified sediments, either a longer digesting time or a harsher alkaline leaching is needed to dissolve all diatoms. This is attributed to increased resistance of diatoms to Na_2CO_3 leaching as a result of reduced surface area and/or improved SiO_2 tetrahedron ordering during diagenetic processes over time and burial depths. Lithogenic silicate minerals can be dissolved by NaOH and potentially separated from diatoms if the latter is completely removed in the preceding leaching steps. Even if a trace amount of diatom is left undissolved in the NaOH leaching, it is still possible to separate the two through a mass balance calculation given the knowledge of composition for the two end-members. We conclude that a successful separation of Si phases in diagenetically modified sediments relies on the knowledge of elemental abundance and even $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values of the leachates, as well as information such as species of Si-skeleton organisms, contents and maturation degree of biogenic silica.

1. Introduction

In the global silicon (Si) cycle, marine sediments represent a critical long-term Si reservoir that is directly connected to the oceans. Pelagic sediments consist of three major Si phases: lithogenic silicate (LSi, such as quartz, feldspar and illite), biogenic silica (BSi or opal, such as diatom frustules and sponge spicules) and authigenic silica/silicate (in-situ precipitation of amorphous and/or clay Si in sediments) (Sutton et al.,

2018; Tréguer et al., 2021). The different Si phases serve as useful archives for key physicochemical processes acting over the Earth history. For example, the downcore BSi content can be used to infer past primary production (Colman and Bratton, 2003; Romero and Hebbeln, 2003; Hendry and Brzezinski, 2014), while LSi composition reflects changes in continental weathering intensity as well as sediment transport (Robert and Kennett, 1997; Opfergelt and Delmelle, 2012; Bi et al., 2015). During sediment burial, early diagenetic processes modify Si

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2023.121681>

Received 4 May 2023; Received in revised form 5 August 2023; Accepted 13 August 2023

Available online 14 August 2023

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compositions by (1) dissolving BSi and/or LSi while inducing authigenic silica/silicate co-precipitation (Michalopoulos and Aller, 1995; Galán, 2006) and (2) transformation of BSi from opal-A to opal-CT (Williams and Crerar, 1985; Williams et al., 1985; Varkouhi et al., 2021). Both processes can alter primary Si signals and thus make interpretation of sediment records difficult. A reliable method to separate different Si phases is of vital importance in order to derive meaningful interpretations and discussion for paleoceanographic conditions.

Wet chemistry leaching has been commonly applied to marine sediments for isolating different Si phases (e.g. DeMaster, 1981; Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Rahman et al., 2016; Krause et al., 2017; Pickering et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2022). For example, DeMaster (1981) extracted BSi through sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) leaching of surficial marine sediments based on dissolution experiments using fresh diatoms (DeMaster, 1981, 1979) which were completely dissolved upon contact with Na_2CO_3 within 2 hours (h). The subsequential increase in Si contents during leaching was interpreted to represent continuous LSi dissolution (DeMaster, 1981). Müller and Schneider (1993) used 1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) instead of Na_2CO_3 to dissolve other BSi species (e.g. sponge) that have lower dissolution rate in Na_2CO_3 than diatoms. More recently, sequential leaching protocols consisting of different wet chemistry treatments have been used to separate different Si phases relying on the contrasting dissolution rate of target Si phases to different reaction conditions, such as leachates pH and reaction temperature (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Rahman et al., 2016; Pickering et al., 2020). Rahman et al. (2016) analyzed naturally occurring radioactive Si isotope (^{32}Si) in marine sediments via a sequential leaching method and concluded that BSi burial rate in deltaic sediment is higher than the estimates from numerical model extrapolation. Pickering et al. (2020) identified different Si phases based on the stable silicon isotopic compositions ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) of hydrochloric acid (HCl), Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leachates in shallow coastal sediments and showed up to 5‰ of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ difference between the three leachates. However, concerns arise due to the mixed Si phases (BSi, LSi and authigenic silica/silicate) in marine sediments and their overlapped solubilities that complicate the isolation of Si phases (Foster, 1953; Barão et al., 2015; Gaboreau et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2023).

Despite the apparent limitations, the methodology proposed by DeMaster (1981) (“DeMaster protocol” hereafter) has been widely adopted for diatom quantification regardless of the age, location and diagenetic modification state of sediments (e.g. Romero et al., 2015; Ota et al., 2019; Sha et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022). The main assumption that all diatoms can be readily dissolved via the DeMaster protocol has rarely been validated to date (Zhu et al., 2023). A few studies have made efforts to quantify dissolution of non-BSi phases (e.g. LSi) in Na_2CO_3 by using analysis of elemental abundances such as aluminium (Al) and potassium (K) (Kamatani and Oku, 2000; Koning et al., 2002; Ragueneau et al., 2005; Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Zhu et al., 2023). They concluded that a significant portion of non-BSi phases could dissolve in the first hour of Na_2CO_3 leaching, and it would cause a potential BSi over-estimation. Furthermore, the DeMaster protocol was initially developed

for fresh diatoms in surficial sediments that have undergone minimal early diagenetic modification. It is, however, unclear how sediment burial and the associated geochemical changes affect the protocol. Other investigations suggested that the DeMaster protocol may underestimate contributions of diatoms that are coated by clay-like materials (defined as the amorphous clay pre-cursors forming in an early stage of the reverse weathering/weathering process) and thus suggested pre-leaching with HCl to improve diatom recovery (Mortlock and Froelich, 1989; Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004). Iwasaki et al. (2014) observed that not all the diatoms in Eocene sediments were readily dissolved by Na_2CO_3 and a substantial amount of diatoms was dissolved when treated with NaOH. These early studies raise critical concerns over the applicability of the DeMaster protocol in diatom quantification for sediments from the deeper subsurface. Therefore, a systematic examination of the DeMaster protocol for deep-sea sediments is essential for studies of paleoceanography, subsurface Si cycling and diagenesis.

This study aims to test how sequential leaching methods, including the DeMaster protocol, can be applied to deeply-buried sediments that have experienced extensive diagenesis, including sulfate reduction, methanogenesis and silicate/silica alteration (“diagenetically-modified sediments” hereafter; Berner, 1980) over millions of year. Our Ulleung Basin deep-sea sediment is the ideal material to study since various diagenesis processes have been documented (Hong et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2016) and deserve a more detailed study in subsurface Si fluid-sediment cycling. It is important to note that we focus on how each Si phase dissolves during leaching instead of comparing with the different leaching protocols since the design of them varies slightly (Table 1). Leachates and leached sediments were examined by a combination of scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), elemental contents (Si, Al, K and Iron (Fe)), as well as stable Si isotopic ratios ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$), to characterize the extracted Si phases (Table 1).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

Sediment samples were obtained from a 218 m long core (UBGH2-1_1) located on the western lower slope of the Ulleung Basin in the East/Japan Sea (36° 15′ 04.8″ N, 130° 03′ 56.6″ E) at a water depth of 1534 m. The drill core was collected during the Second Ulleung Basin Gas Hydrate Drilling Expedition (UBGH2) in 2010 (Ryu et al., 2013). The sediment accumulation rate is around 12.7 cm/ky (Bahk et al., 2016). Sediments are mainly composed of hemipelagic mud with occasional mass-transport deposits and volcanic ashes accumulated since the Pleistocene (Bahk et al., 2016). Quartz, muscovite and albite are the primary detrital minerals, and illite is the main clay mineral in the sediments (Lee et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2016). High amounts of opal-A have been reported in the study region based on XRD estimates (opal-A includes BSi and non-BSi amorphous material in this XRD-based method; Lee et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2016). Microscopic images suggest that diatom frustules are the main component to provide such high

Table 1
Comparison of sequential leaching protocols.

Leaching method	Michalopoulos and Aller (2004)	Pickering et al. (2020)	Ward et al. (2022)	This study
Core length	Medium (2–3 m) & Short sediment core (< 0.5 m)	Short sediment core (< 0.5 m)		Drill core sediment (9 to 207 m)
Material	Deltic Sediment	Continental shelf sediment		Continental slope sediment
Leachate		HCl, Na_2CO_3 and NaOH		HCl, Na_2CO_3 , NaOH and Alkaline Fusion
Elemental Analysis	Si and K	Si	Si, Al, Ti, Fe, Mn, Mg and V	Si, Al, Fe and K
Si isotope Analysis		^{32}Si	$\delta^{30}\text{Si}$	$\delta^{30}\text{Si}$
XRD and SEM Analysis	SEM			XRD and SEM

BSi content (Bahk et al., 2013). Geothermal gradient is as high as 100 °C/km at our study site (Lee et al., 2013). Total organic carbon content (TOC) is generally higher than 1 wt% with marine algae origin (Hong et al., 2013; Choi et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2014). Ten sediment samples from 9 to 207 m below seafloor (mbsf) were selected for this study (Table S1). Sediment samples that were used for leaching in this study were collected from compacted sediments after shipboard pore-water extraction. Samples were stored under 4 °C since 2010 and were freeze-dried before leaching.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Sequential leaching steps

The modified sequential leaching method used in this study is illustrated in Fig. 1a. About 1 g of freeze-dried sediment was first treated with 3 vol/vol% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂; EMSURE®, Merck) to remove organic matter following the protocol of Mortlock and Froelich (1989). The pretreatment terminated when the bubbling ceased, which usually took 15 h. Sediments were then rinsed with Milli-Q water (resistivity 18.2 MΩ-cm) until the H₂O₂ was completely removed as indicated by peroxide test strips (MQuant®, Supleco).

The H₂O₂ pre-treated sediments were then reacted motionless with 40 ml 0.1 M trace metal clean HCl (Suprapur®, Supleco) at room temperature (around 20 °C) for 13 h. After centrifugation, supernatant was collected for analysis. To wash away the residual acid, sediments were rinsed with 50 ml Milli-Q water and centrifuged (6500 rpm for 7 min) to separate the solid and liquid phases. This rinsing step was carried out

until the supernatant was nearly neutral in pH, as an indication of complete removal of HCl. The washed sediments were then air-dried in a fume hood.

The acid-leached sediments were further treated with 40 ml 1 wt% Na₂CO₃ solution that was prepared from anhydrous Na₂CO₃ powder (Ph. Eur./NF/BP, VWR). The reaction took place in a motionless 85 °C water bath for 5 h. A 2.5 ml aliquot of the supernatants was collected at 1, 2, 3 and 5 h of leaching. The four aliquots were diluted five times with Milli-Q water and acidified with trace metal clean nitric acid (0.5 ml 65% HNO₃, Suprapur®, Supleco) for storage. After 5 h of leaching, the remnant fluid was separated from solids through centrifuging and discarded. The residual sediments were rinsed with Milli-Q water following the same procedure described above.

The residual sediments were then leached with 12 ml 4 M NaOH solution that was prepared from NaOH powder (Suprapur®, Sigma-Aldrich). The reaction took place in a motionless 85 °C water bath for three hours. A 0.5 ml aliquot of the supernatant was collected at 1 and 3 h of leaching each. These leachates were diluted 50 times with Milli-Q water and HNO₃-acidified (0.5 ml 65% HNO₃) for storage. The identical Milli-Q water rinse procedure was applied to sediments as described above.

To establish a lithogenic end-member within the sediments, a portion of the leached sediments was completely digested via alkaline fusion. Between 2 and 4 mg of leached sediment and 20 mg of the NaOH powder were loaded into a silver crucible and placed in a 550 °C high-temperature furnace for 10 min. After cooling to room temperature, the NaOH-fused sediment was transferred to a Teflon container by

Fig. 1. (a) Leaching protocol and (b) scheme of replicated leaching steps in this study. Four parallel leaching experiments were conducted for five out of ten samples. Experiments were stopped at HCl-13 h, Na₂CO₃-5 h, NaOH-1 h and NaOH-3 h for the four parallel experiments. Leachates were collected during parallel experiments so that there are four replicates of HCl leachate, three replicates of Na₂CO₃ leachate (1, 2, 3 and 5 h) and two replicates of NaOH-1 h for each selected sample. Leached sediments were collected after selected leaching steps (i.e. HCl-13 h, Na₂CO₃-5 h, NaOH-1 h and NaOH-3 h) for microscopic analyses.

immersing the crucible into Milli-Q water loading container. Five ml of 1 M trace metal clean HCl (Suprapur®, Supleco) was then added to dissolve the fused sediment overnight at room temperature. The resulting solution was then diluted to 50 ml (10 times dilution) for storage and analysis. We note that the concentration of HCl used during alkaline fusion needs to be carefully adjusted (around neutral pH) so that neither metal oxide (acidic) nor silicon polymers (basic) formation is induced. The exact HCl concentration depended on the sediment composition and the amounts of NaOH added.

2.2.2. Replication of sequential leaching method

Five (out of ten) sediment samples were selected for a parallel leaching scheme (Fig. 1b). For each of the five samples, four parallel leaching experiments (a total 20 experiments) were carried out following the aforementioned protocol (see Section 2.2.1) but terminated at different steps for each of the four parallel experiments: 13 h of HCl leaching (HCl-13 h), 5 h of Na₂CO₃ leaching (Na₂CO₃-5 h), 1 h of NaOH leaching (NaOH-1 h), and 3 h of NaOH leaching (NaOH-3 h). In other words, after the parallel leaching of the five selected samples, there were four replicates for HCl leachate, three replicates for 5-h Na₂CO₃ leaching, and two replicates for 1-h NaOH leaching (Fig. 1b). Such a scheme aims to test the reproducibility of the sequential leaching in terms of the elemental abundance (Si, Al, K, Fe and δ³⁰Si) in the leachate. In addition, the parallel treatment also allows sufficient sediment material (ca. 500 mg) for mineral and amorphous material abundance quantification (Section 2.2.5). For alkaline fusion, two samples were selected for duplication (samples from depths 9 and 48 mbsf).

2.2.3. Elemental composition of the leachate

Leachate samples were first diluted so that all target elements concentrations were within instrumental calibration curves (10 to 10,000 ppb) for inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES; ICAP 6000 series, Thermo Scientific) at the Department of Geological Sciences, Stockholm University. Samples were acidified with HNO₃ (10 vol %) before analyses. We focus on Si, Al and Fe for the detection of silicate minerals and metal oxides as well as calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) for the detection of carbonate dissolution. Overall analytical errors for all measured elements were <4% as determined by repetitive analyses of international (NIST 1634f) and in-house standards. Blank solutions (HCl, Na₂CO₃ and NaOH) were also measured for correcting background and monitoring contamination (Na, Mg and K are the main contaminations for HCl, Na₂CO₃ and NaOH leaching solutions, respectively. The level of contamination is <75 ppb).

2.2.4. Silicon isotopes

Leachates were first diluted with Milli-Q water so that Si concentrations are around 9 ppm. Si in the diluted leachates was isolated using cation exchange columns (Georg et al., 2006). Each column was packed with 1 ml cation exchange resin (Bio-Rad AG®50 W-X12, 100–200 mesh). The purification consisted of four steps: (1) pre-cleaning of columns with 3 ml of HCl loadings (three times using 4 M, 8 M and 4 M, respectively), (2) conditioning of the columns with 6 ml of Milli-Q water, (3) loading 2 ml of the diluted leachates onto the column and (4) elution of Si with 4 ml Milli-Q water. To ensure a full recovery and prevent any Si isotope fractionation during purification, Si concentrations were measured in the eluted fluids using the molybdate-blue spectrophotometric approach (Pettersson and Karlberg, 1999) with a spectrophotometer (810 nm; Evolution 260 BIO, Thermo Scientific) at the Department of Geological Sciences, Stockholm University. The recovery of Si through the columns was >97%.

Si isotopic compositions (²⁸Si, ²⁹Si and ³⁰Si) of purified samples (2–3 ppm of Si) were measured using a multicollector-inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (Nu Plasma II MC-ICP-MS, Nu Instruments Ltd.) coupled with an ESI Apex HF desolvating nebulizer (~100 μL min⁻¹ uptake rate) at the Vegacenter, Swedish Museum of Natural History, Sweden. All samples were diluted to around 1 ppm Si and doped

with 2 ppm Li to match the matrix of international standards prepared by LiBO₂ fusion (Diatomite, IRMM-018 and Big Batch; Reynolds et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2010). These standards were routinely measured during sample analyses. Silicon isotope values were expressed as δ³⁰Si by normalized to the international Si standard NBS-28:

$$\delta^{30}\text{Si} = \left(R_{\text{Sample}} / R_{\text{Standard}} - 1 \right) \times 1000$$

where R is ³⁰Si/²⁸Si in the sample and standard. The measured δ³⁰Si values for the Diatomite, IRMM-018 and Big Batch (three standards) were 1.2 ± 0.1 (2σ; n = 28), -1.8 ± 0.1 (2σ; n = 11), and -10.6 ± 0.1 ‰ (2σ; n = 11), respectively which agrees with the published values (Reynolds et al., 2007; Hendry et al., 2011). Mass-dependent isotopic fractionations between δ³⁰Si and δ²⁹Si of all measurements are consistent with the kinetic mass fractionation law (Reynolds et al., 2007):

$$\delta^{29}\text{Si} = 0.51 \times \delta^{30}\text{Si} \quad (n = 70; R^2 = 0.997; p\text{-value} < 0.0001)$$

2.2.5. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopic (SEM)

About 100 mg of dried post-leached sediment was homogenized with around 5 mg of zinc oxide (ZnO) by using an agate mortar and pestle. Unoriented preparations were transferred to a low background sample holder cut from a Si-monocrystal wafer. The mineral compositions of the samples were measured with a Bruker D8 diffractometer using Ni-filtered CuKα radiation over the 2–75° 2θ region in the Department of Geology, University of Tartu, Estonia. Quantitative mineral compositions were determined by full-profile Rietveld algorithm-based analysis with Siroquant 3.0 code (Taylor, 1991).

The content of non-diffracting amorphous phase was estimated through a Rietveld and reference intensity ratio method (Rietveld-RIR method; Gualtieri, 2000) by applying a spike of a known standard (ZnO). The overestimation of mineral contents due to the miscount of amorphous phases can be calibrated through the internal standard. The weight differences between bulk samples and minerals were attributed to the weight of amorphous material.

Micromorphology and spatial relationship of studied leached samples were investigated with SEM (ZEISS, EVO MA 15) in the Department of Geology, University of Tartu, Estonia. For preparation, a few mg of samples was transferred onto a carbon tape. The platinum-coated samples were imaged and analyzed in a high vacuum setting. The chemical compositions of the phases were analyzed using an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS; Oxford Aztec X-Max).

3. Results

3.1. XRD

The whole rock compositions of bulk and leached sediments are presented in Table S2. The dominant minerals in the bulk sediments from the Ulleung Basin are quartz, plagioclase, mica, and illite (18 ± 3 wt%, 11 ± 1 wt%, 12 ± 3 wt%, and 10 ± 3 wt%, respectively; 1σ; n = 5). Other minor phases are illitic mixed layer illite-smectite, kaolinite, chlorite, smectitic mixed layer illite-smectite, k-feldspar (5 ± 2 wt%, 4 ± 1 wt%, 3 ± 1 wt%, 3 ± 2 wt%, and 3 ± 1 wt%, respectively). The amorphous content decreases during leaching steps. The highest average amorphous content (27 ± 2 wt%; 1σ; n = 5) was detected in bulk sediments, 20 ± 13 wt% in HCl leached sediments, 13 ± 8 wt% in Na₂CO₃ leached sediments, 11 ± 6 wt% in NaOH-1 h leached, and the lowest amount was found in NaOH-3 h leached sediments (5 ± 4 wt%).

3.2. Leachate composition

Si contents in leachates collected from all ten samples display a wide range: 15.0–39.3 μmol Si g⁻¹ (dry sediment) in HCl leachates, 69.8–465 μmol Si g⁻¹ in Na₂CO₃ leachates (including 1, 2, 3 and 5 h), 367–2621 μmol Si g⁻¹ in NaOH leachates (including 1 and 3 h) and 7830–11,177

Fig. 2. (a) Elemental contents, (b) elemental ratios and (c) stable Si isotopic values for the different leaching steps. Leaching steps are separated by dotted vertical lines, and AF denotes the alkaline fusion step.

$\mu\text{mol Si g}^{-1}$ in alkaline fused residuals (Fig. 2a and Table S1).

The Al contents range from 23.7 to 43.4 $\mu\text{mol Al g}^{-1}$ in HCl leachates, 1.0–4.8 $\mu\text{mol Al g}^{-1}$ in Na_2CO_3 leachates, 94.1–292 $\mu\text{mol Al g}^{-1}$ in NaOH leachates and 2468–3231 $\mu\text{mol Al g}^{-1}$ in alkaline fused residual. The K contents range from 5.5 to 15.1 $\mu\text{mol K g}^{-1}$ in HCl leachates, 2.7–13.6 $\mu\text{mol K g}^{-1}$ in Na_2CO_3 leachates, 9.0–58.7 $\mu\text{mol K g}^{-1}$ in NaOH leachates and 469–720 $\mu\text{mol K g}^{-1}$ in alkaline fused residuals. Lastly, the Fe contents range from 13.9 to 101 $\mu\text{mol Fe g}^{-1}$ in HCl leachates, 0.3–1.7 $\mu\text{mol Fe g}^{-1}$ in Na_2CO_3 leachates, 7.2–23.5 $\mu\text{mol Fe g}^{-1}$ in NaOH leachates and 339–704 $\mu\text{mol Fe g}^{-1}$ in the alkaline fused residual (Fig. 2a and Table S1). Notably, some fine fractions might be lost during the Milli-Q wash. Future work is needed to quantify such a missing and calculate the recovery after Milli-Q wash.

3.3. Silicon isotope values ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) from various leaching steps

Si isotope values of HCl leachates ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{HCl}}$) range from -1.8 to -0.8‰ with an average of $-1.3 \pm 0.4\text{‰}$ (1σ ; $n = 10$; Fig. 2c; Table S1). The Si isotopic composition of Na_2CO_3 leachates, $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3}$, ranges from 1.1 to 1.8‰ (Fig. 2c; Table S1). The $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3}$ values from the first hour ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3-1\text{h}}$) are similar to those from the fifth hour ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3-5\text{h}}$), with the former ranging from 1.1 to 1.6‰ and the latter from 1.1 to 1.8‰ (Fig. 2c; Table S1). The Si isotope values of NaOH leachate ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{NaOH}}$) range from -0.5 to 1.2‰ and are higher than $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{HCl}}$ values but lower than $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3}$ values (Table S1). The Si isotope values of the NaOH leachates during the first hour ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{NaOH-1h}}$) have similar values (-0.5 to 1.2‰) than that of the third hour ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{NaOH-3h}}$; -0.6 to 1.0‰ ; Fig. 2c; Table S1). The final residuals dissolved by the alkaline fusion encompass a narrow $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ range of -0.4 to -0.2‰ (Fig. 2c; Table S1).

4. Discussion

4.1. Leaching reproducibility

Relative standard deviation (RSD (%); standard deviation/mean \times

100) is used for determining the leaching reproducibility for elemental contents when comparing our results with previous studies (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Pickering et al., 2020). Such a choice of statistical method is due to the different absolute concentrations in the various leaching solutions (HCl, Na_2CO_3 and NaOH; Fig. S1b and S1c) and among studies from different locations (e.g. continental margin and deltaic environments; Table 1). The RSD reflects the scattering of replicated measurements related to the mean values with higher percentages indicating greater scattering of repeated analyses of the same sample (Fig. 3). For Si isotope values, the reproducibility can be simply compared since the $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values have already been normalized to an international standard. As compared to previous studies, similar or lower RSDs for Si and K contents in HCl, Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leaching (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Pickering et al., 2020; Fig. 3) were found in our leachates. Similar standard deviations of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ (Georg et al., 2006; Pickering et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2022) are also observed. This provides confidence in our modified leaching method. Collectively, considering all the replicate measurements (Si, Al, Fe and K) as one sample group (128 RSDs in total), the 95% confidence level of RSDs ranges from 2 to 58%, meaning that the standard deviation of most replicates is less than half of the mean value. High variability (i.e. RSD over 58%) could be attributed to low elemental concentrations in the leachate (for example, Fe content in Na_2CO_3 leachate; Fig. S1a) that were close to the detection limit of ICP-OES. Therefore, we do not include these results in the following discussion.

4.2. Dissolution of the amorphous secondary Si phase in HCl leaching

The lowest ratios of Si to other elements were observed from HCl leachate as compared to other leachates (Fig. 2b). The low Si-to-element ratios in HCl leachates indicate the dissolution of Fe oxide and clay-like material (Childs, 1992; Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004). The values of elemental ratios derived from stoichiometric regression lines support this conclusion (Fig. S2). For example, the Si/Fe (0.3 mol mol^{-1}) and Si/K ratios (1.9 mol mol^{-1}) from regression lines (Fig. S2) are similar to the

Fig. 3. Comparison of relative standard deviations (RSD; standard deviation of elemental content/mean elemental content; %) of elemental content from this study and previous work (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Pickering et al., 2020) in box and whisker plots. The number of measurements in each study is presented as n (e.g. five selected samples for replication in this study). The right, middle and left panels are the results from HCl, Na₂CO₃ and NaOH leachates, respectively. Boxes indicate 25, 50 and 75 percentiles and whiskers are minimum and maximum.

Si/Fe ratios of Fe oxide (0.2 to 0.4 mol mol⁻¹) from Childs (1992) and Si/K ratios in clay-like material (2.6 mol mol⁻¹ in HCl leaching) from Michalopoulos and Aller (2004). Our interpretation of leached Fe oxide and clay-like material is also supported by the SEM-EDS analysis showing aggregates with high Fe and O abundances in the original sample (Fig. 4a). After HCl leaching, such aggregates disappeared as indicated by SEM observations (Fig. 4b). Besides the amorphous secondary Si phases, carbonate is also dissolved during HCl leaching, as indicated by the high Ca and Mg contents detected in the leachates (Table S1). Some of the Mg in HCl leachates potentially come from dissolution of clay, as Mg-to-Ca ratios in these leachates are much higher than the expected ratios for carbonate minerals (Table S1).

The low Si isotopic values from our HCl leachates (−1.8 to −0.8 ‰) match with those reported previously for secondary clay and/or Fe oxide (−3 to 3 ‰; Ziegler et al., 2005; Georg et al., 2007; Méheut et al., 2007; Delstanche et al., 2009; Opfergelt et al., 2009; Opfergelt and Delmelle, 2012) and can be explained by the preferable adsorption of light Si isotopes onto the Fe or manganese (Mn) oxide surfaces (Oelze et al., 2014). Our δ³⁰Si from HCl leachates are nonetheless higher than the values from the HCl leachate of other studies (−3.2 to −2.6 ‰; Pickering et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2022). This can be attributed to the variable HCl-leachable Si phases and/or different origins (in-situ vs detritus) from different study areas (Table 1). Fe oxide can also form in-situ or through pyrite oxidation during storage (König et al., 2001). We cannot completely exclude the possibility of post-cruise Fe oxide formation as the sediments are Fe-rich. Micro-molar level of Fe²⁺ was detected in porewater throughout the core (Kim et al., 2016), indicating potential fast reductive dissolution of Fe oxide. Collectively, we conclude that the HCl-leachable Si phases from the investigated site are most likely represented by Si adsorption onto Fe oxide and clay-like material (“Amorphous Secondary Si phase” or ASSi thereafter). Currently, we neither

have information for its structure nor time of formation and thus cannot conclude whether ASSi was formed in situ or transported from land.

4.3. Diatom dissolution during Na₂CO₃ leaching

The δ³⁰Si_{Na₂CO₃} values (1.1 to 1.8 ‰) were found to be in the range of typical δ³⁰Si_{diatom} (−1 to 3 ‰; De La Rocha et al., 2000; Cardinal et al., 2007; Sutton et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2014; Frings et al., 2016) suggest the predominant role of diatoms in Na₂CO₃ leachates. The other BSi species such as radiolarians, though characterized by similar Si isotope signatures (0.6 to 1.7 ‰; Doering et al., 2021), their contributions to the overall BSi pool is limited based on the previous findings (Bahk et al., 2013; section 2.1). In the first hour of Na₂CO₃ leaching, relatively high K and Al concentrations were measured as compared to the leachates from later hours (Fig. S3). This release of K and Al is attributed to the dissolution of residual ASSi from HCl leaching. A similar observation was made by others that ASSi is responsible for the K released in the first two hours of Na₂CO₃ leaching (Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004). The Si addition from ASSi is, however, insignificant with respect to the overall Si content in Na₂CO₃ leaching (Fig. 2a). Assuming the Si/K ratios of ASSi as determined from our HCl leachates, we calculated a Si contribution from the residual ASSi in Na₂CO₃ leachates as 13.2 ± 10.9 μmol Si g⁻¹ (1σ; n = 10; Supplementary Materials) or <5% of all Si leached in this step (282 ± 98 μmol Si g⁻¹; 1σ; n = 10). ASSi also has a negligible effect on δ³⁰Si. This is demonstrated by the minor differences between δ³⁰Si_{Na₂CO₃-1h} and δ³⁰Si_{Na₂CO₃-5h} (1.1 to 1.6 ‰ and 1.1 to 1.8 ‰, respectively; Fig. 2c) despite the higher K content in the first-hour leachate of Na₂CO₃.

The increasing Si/Al and Si/K ratios from Na₂CO₃-1 h to Na₂CO₃-5 h (Fig. S3) and consistently high δ³⁰Si values in Na₂CO₃ leachates (Fig. 2c) suggest that a dominant Si contribution from diatom dissolution during

Fig. 4. SEM images of (a) bulk sediment with Fe-rich aggregate coatings. The elemental contents of aggregates were measured by EDS. (b) Fe-rich aggregates were not observed after HCl leaching. Apparent diatom pieces remain after leaching, as shown by the images after (c) Na₂CO₃ leaching and (d) NaOH-1 h leaching.

the entire Na₂CO₃ leaching. This observation contrasts the observation made by DeMaster (1981) that diatom could be completely dissolved after the first two hours of Na₂CO₃ leaching. We propose that such a discrepancy can be attributed to the structural changes in frustules of fresh and diagenetically-modified diatoms. Fresh diatoms dissolved rapidly in Na₂CO₃ leaching, while post-depositional diagenesis makes diatoms more resistant to Na₂CO₃ leaching due to the silica structure transformation as a result of higher temperature, higher pressure and longer burial time (Calvert, 1975; Kastner et al., 1977). In other words, burial maturation makes deeply-buried diatoms more difficult to be digested by Na₂CO₃. Inspection of the Si-O-Si bonds in diatom silica by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic

resonance demonstrated that fresh diatoms from laboratory cultures contain less Si-O-Si bonds; (i.e. bridge bonding between tetrahedral SiO₂), while mature diatoms have denser and well-defined Si-phase structures compared to the fresh ones (Schmidt et al., 2001; Gendron-Badou et al., 2003; Fig. 5). The differences in tetrahedral SiO₂ bonding result in a more leaching-resistant diatom following maturation (Fig. 5). Similarly, a progressive reduction in the specific surface area of diatoms was observed with burial depth, which makes mature diatoms less susceptible to leaching attack (Hurd, 1973; Hurd and Theyer, 1975, 1977; McManus et al., 1995; Van Cappellen, 1996; Van Cappellen and Qiu, 1997a,b). These two factors would decrease the dissolution rate during diatom maturation (Willey, 1980; Williams et al., 1985).

Fig. 5. Structural transformation of diatom during diagenesis. Original diatom structure is featured with hydroxyl bonds that participate in various surface reactions (e.g. adsorption and dissolution). Compaction and heating cause dehydration during burial and increase the bridge bonding between SiO₂ tetrahedrons. This transformation changes the property (crystallinity, reactive surface area, dissolution rate and resistance to Na₂CO₃) of the diatom. The changes in font size from fresh to mature diatoms indicate the increase or decrease of property values. Take crystallinity as an example; the increase in font size of crystallinity from fresh to mature indicates an increase in the crystallinity of diatom as suggested by Williams et al. (1985).

Besides the decreasing dissolution rate due to changes in bond orientation and surface area, clay or clay-like material (described as ASSi in our study) coatings have also been shown to affect the leachability of diatoms (Dixit et al., 2001; Michalopoulos and Aller, 2004; Rahman et al., 2017). Especially, Michalopoulos and Aller (2004) demonstrated that diatom could not be readily dissolved by Na_2CO_3

leaching without HCl pretreatment. Acids remove clay-like material formed on the diatom surface and thus promote diatom dissolution in Na_2CO_3 leaching. This is, however, not likely to be the case in our study, as our samples have been treated with HCl for over 13 h prior to Na_2CO_3 leaching to remove surficial clay and/or ASSi (Fig. 1). Our results thus favour the explanation that changes in diatom structure and/or

Fig. 6. (a) (b) Plots of (Si/Al and Si/K) vs. stable Si isotopic signatures, $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$. Yellow triangles are the values of NaOH-1 h leachates, and blue stars indicate the results of the NaOH-3 h leachates. (c) A binary mixing model considers Si/K and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$. Yellow triangles are the NaOH-1 h leachates, and blue stars indicate the results of the NaOH-3 h leachates. Redline is the binary mixing curve between diatom and LSi end-members, and red ticks are the diatom fraction in the mixture. The end-member values for diatom are Si/K = 1000 mol mol⁻¹ and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ = 1.5‰ that were assigned, based on an assumed trace amount of K in diatom and the average value of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-5h}}$. The LSi_{NaOH} end-member represents a fraction of the lithogenic Si signal that can be extracted by NaOH leaching. The Si/K and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values for this end-member were derived from measured values of NaOH-1 to 3 h experiments from 32 mbsf, a sample that has the lowest $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ (12.1 mol mol⁻¹ and -4.1 ‰ for Si/K and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$, respectively; Supplementary Materials). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

decreasing surface areas during burial maturation is the primary explanation for our observations. Change in the assemblage of BSi (e.g. diatom vs sponge) may also impact Na_2CO_3 leaching efficiency as the dissolution rate differs among BSi species due to their structure differences (Coradin and Lopez, 2003). For instance, Maldonado et al. (2019) showed that sponge skeletons are more resistant to Na_2CO_3 leaching than diatoms. Nonetheless, the prolonged dissolution in our experiment cannot be explained by the dissolution of a different BSi community such as sponges that have significantly lower $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values than those of diatoms (−6 to 0 ‰; De La Rocha, 2003; Wille et al., 2010; Hendry and Robinson, 2012; Frings et al., 2016; Fig. 2c). No such low $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values were observed from our Na_2CO_3 leaching (Fig. 2c).

4.4. Mixing of diatom and lithogenic silicate in NaOH leaching: issues of quantifying biogenic silica in diagenetically modified sediments

Good correlations between $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{NaOH}}$ and Si/Al or Si/K ratios can be observed in NaOH leachates (Fig. 6a and b), indicating a mixture of two distinct Si phases: 1) remaining diatoms with high $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values and Si/K (and Si/Al) ratios and 2) NaOH-leachable LSi (LSi_{NaOH}), a phase calculated through Si mass balance equation, features low $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values and Si/K (and Si/Al) ratios. The Si isotope composition of this phase is potentially attributed to preferential releasing light Si isotope during the early stage of mineral dissolution (a detailed discussion of its definition is described in Supplementary Materials). To better quantify the remaining diatom carried over to NaOH leaching, we performed a binary mixing calculation in a correlation diagram between $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and Si/K assuming two end-members (Fig. 6c; detail described in the Supplementary Materials). This calculation was conducted assuming that diatom is the main dissolving BSi species during NaOH leaching and the contribution of other BSi species is limited. This assumption is based on the diatom dominance in Ulleung Basin (Bahk et al., 2013; Section 2.1) and apparent diatom fragments after five hours of Na_2CO_3 leaching (Fig. 4c and d). We estimated high contributions of Si from diatoms, ranging from 62 to 91% of total Si in NaOH leachates from shallow to deep sediments (column (c) in Table 2) in the NaOH leachates, suggesting that significant amounts of diatoms are left after Na_2CO_3 leaching.

The high amounts of diatom dissolved in NaOH leachates result in a stark underestimation of total BSi abundance if one assumes all diatoms are dissolved by Na_2CO_3 as in the DeMaster protocol. For the samples from diagenetically modified sediments in Ulleung Basin, we estimated diatom contents of 58.7 to 346 $\mu\text{mol Si g}^{-1}$ based on the DeMaster protocol (or up to 2 wt%; column (d) in Table 2). When including diatoms dissolved during NaOH leaching, the estimated amounts of diatom increased by 3.8 to 15.4 times as compared to the estimates through the DeMaster protocol (column (f) in Table 2), ranging from 490 to 2757 $\mu\text{mol Si g}^{-1}$ (or 3 to 17 wt%, column (e) in Table 2). Such a

discrepancy is attributed to the neglect of mature diatoms that were more readily dissolved in NaOH (Fig. 5).

Based on our collective observations, we propose an explanation of how the dissolution of mature diatom may proceed during the Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leaching (Fig. 7). Almost immediate dissolution of fresh diatoms in Na_2CO_3 is evident from the sharp increase in Si contents soon after leaching starts (green area in Fig. 7a). However, the mature diatom, due to early diagenetic processes in sediments, dissolves more slowly, resulting in broadened Si maximum (blue line in Fig. 7a). Furthermore, due to the higher resistance to Na_2CO_3 , substantial amounts of diatoms are still left undissolved after 5 h of Na_2CO_3 leaching and are eventually dissolved in NaOH (orange line in Fig. 7a).

Our downcore results of Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leachates also support our interpretation that mature diatoms are more difficult to be dissolved by Na_2CO_3 due to post-depositional diagenesis (Fig. 7b). Our calculation suggests that diatoms in deeper sediments were more resistant to Na_2CO_3 leaching and thus proportionally more diatoms were leached by NaOH as compared to the shallower samples (Fig. 7b). This progressive change in leaching can also be explained by the gradual changes in diatom properties, despite no noticeable change from opal-A to opal-CT based on the downcore XRD result (i.e. no cristobalite or tridymite is detected; Table S2). A similar result has also been shown by Iwasaki et al. (2014), who found poor BSi leaching efficiency when applying Na_2CO_3 leaching to Eocene sediments from the central Arctic Ocean. This observation was attributed to apparent transition from opal-A to opal-CT (Iwasaki et al., 2014).

5. Conclusions and future perspectives

The ability to separate different Si phases from diagenetically-modified and deeply-buried drill core sediments is essential for applications such as paleoceanography reconstruction and sediment source tracing over long geological time scales. This is never been systematically tested until now. We examined the efficiency of sequential leaching in separating Si phases from marine sediments using drill cores from the Ulleung Basin down to 218 mbsf. Our analyses, including solid phase examination as well as $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values and elemental compositions of the leachates, have demonstrated appreciable mixing in every leaching step. This finding emphasizes the importance of having Si isotopic signatures as a critical constraint for the nature of Si phases. We show that HCl leaching is able to dissolve metal oxide or clay-like material together with the Si adsorbed to them (i.e. ASSi). For Na_2CO_3 leaching, trace amounts of ASSi were detected in the first hour. Such a Si contribution is insignificant as the Si from diatom dissolution dominated the overall Si pool over the 5-h leaching period. Large amounts of diatoms remain and are later dissolved by NaOH, leading to a mixing between diatoms and LSi_{NaOH} in our NaOH leachate. To resolve this mixing effect, isotopic and

Table 2

Diatom contribution in Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leachate as well as diatom estimation between this study and the DeMaster protocol.

Sample depth (mbsf)	Diatom contribution ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}/\%$) ^a			Total diatom (wt%)		
	(a) Na_2CO_3	(b) NaOH-1 h ^b	(c) NaOH 3 h ^b	(d) Based on DeMaster (1981)	(e) This study ^c	(f) This study/DeMaster ^d
9	230.4	283.8/67%	454.7/65%	1%	4%	3.8
21	119.7	238.3/65%	370.6/62%	0%	3%	8.4
32	457.9	1024.2/86%	1024.2/82%	2%	9%	4.3
48	380.6	681.3/76%	737.0/69%	2%	7%	4.1
71	287.8	515.1/77%	643.9/73%	1%	6%	5.1
96	230.6	508.9/80%	534.4/74%	1%	5%	4.0
111	245.0	845.6/85%	856.5/75%	1%	7%	4.9
133	284.1	748.8/85%	799.9/79%	1%	7%	5.1
152	210.3	1097.5/92%	1324.0/83%	1%	9%	15.4
207	368.4	2201.3/95%	2384.8/91%	2%	17%	9.8

^a (Diatom content in NaOH)/(Total Si content in NaOH 1 h or NaOH 3 h).

^b Using $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ to calculate (Supplementary 2.3).

^c Using Diatom contribution in NaOH and Na_2CO_3 to calculate (column (a) + (c); Supplementary Materials 2.3).

^d column (e)/ column (d).

Fig. 7. Conceptual BSi leaching progress for our Ulleung Basin sediments based on the measured Si content at leaching time for three depths. See Supplementary Materials for detailed calculation (a) Leaching progress for fresh diatom (green area) and mature diatom in Na_2CO_3 leaching (solid blue line). The plot is based on the results of a sample from 9 mbsf (age around 40 ka). The plot of fresh diatom leaching is based on the laboratory findings of DeMaster (1979). The dark red dashed line is considered both mature diatom and LSi dissolutions in NaOH leaching as compared to the orange line, which only includes the mature diatom dissolution. (b) Diatom leaching progress for sample 9 (solid/dashed light grey line), 71 (age around 400 ka; solid/dashed grey line) and 207 mbsf (age around 1550 ka; solid/dashed black line) during Na_2CO_3 and NaOH leaching. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

elemental content analyses are essential. Previous studies have used Al content (or Si/Al ratio) to calibrate the mixing of clay minerals and BSi (Kamatani and Oku, 2000; Koning et al., 2002; Ragueneau et al., 2005; Zhu et al., 2023). However, without constraints from the $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values, the mixing of diatom signals in NaOH leaching cannot be entirely excluded due to the low Al content in diatoms.

We argue that the decrease in surface area and/or improved SiO_2 tetrahedron ordering of the diatom silica during sediment burial is the primary explanation for the observed changes in diatom dissolution rate. In other words, diagenetically modified diatoms have a lower Na_2CO_3 dissolution rate as compared to that for fresh diatoms. As the investigated sediments are still above the opal-A to opal-CT transition, our observed decreasing diatom dissolution rate indicates a gradual change in diatom structure even in the depths shallower than the transition. Such a gradual transition could be a universal phenomenon at places where sediments underwent diagenesis due to increasing temperature, pressure and burial time.

Despite the significant phase mixing in NaOH leachate, one can still determine the contributions from different end-members if $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and elemental abundances have been measured. The goal to isolate specific Si phases is thus achievable, as exemplified by separating the diatom and LSi_{NaOH} end-members through $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and Si/K ratios in our study.

For future applications of suitable sequential leaching to other diagenetically-modified sediment, we suggest measuring both the elemental (such as Si/Al and Si/K) and Si isotope compositions of leachates and residual sediments as well as evaluating the sources of Si (e.g. constrain BSi source using a separation method such as Kalmychikov et al. (2005)) and the potential mixing among them. Before applying a sequential protocol, assessing the quantity and condition of diatom (or other BSi of interest) using microscopy techniques is recommended. The factors that should be considered include BSi species, content (BSi rich vs. poor) and degree of maturation (fresh vs. mature). In addition, regional information such as subsurface thermal gradient, sediment age and porewater chemistry are important to assess the diagenetic stages of BSi. For method improvement, the fine fractions of origin and samples are recommended to be measured to evaluate the fine fractions loss during Milli-Q wash.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Wei-Li Hong reports financial support from Ragnar Söderbergs stiftelse, European Research Council, and Swedish Research Council.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge Ragnar Söderbergs stiftelse (project number: 1/22-A) for the generous financial support through the scheme of Swedish Foundations' Starting Grant. We also acknowledge the financial support from European Research Council (ERC) through the Consolidator grant (Project 101087884 — MadSilica). J.-H.K. acknowledges the support from the Korea Ministry of Science and ICT (GP2021-009). The authors also receive financial and technical support from NordSIM-Vegacenter for the analyses of stable silicon isotopes. NordSIMS-Vegacenter is funded by the Swedish Research Council as a national research infrastructure (Dnr. 2021-00276). This is Vegacenter publication number 065.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2023.121681>.

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